

关于新型智能合约欺诈行为研究的调查 (interview 部分)

本工作主要聚焦于一种新型智能合约欺诈行为，并提出了一种专门用于检测的工具 CompileGuard，因此在本部分中将给出问卷部分各合约的检测结果。请结合您在第一部分中的回答感受，回答以下问题：

第一部分：示例合约检测结果

合约 1:

```
1 contract AssetManager {
2     ...
3     function deposit() public payable {
4         require(msg.value > 0, "Deposit amount must be greater than zero");
5         balances[msg.sender] += msg.value;
6     }
7     function withdraw(uint256 amount) public {
8         require(balances[msg.sender] >= amount, "Insufficient balance");
9         balances[msg.sender] -= amount;
10        payable(msg.sender).transfer(amount);
11    }
12    function setAssetId(uint256 newId) public {
13        require(msg.sender == owner, "Only the owner can set the asset ID");
14        uint256 r1;
15        assembly {
16            mstore(0x40, newId)
17            r1 := keccak256(0x40, 0x20)
18        }
19        assetId = r1;
20    }
21    function getAssetId() public view returns (uint256) {
22        return assetId;
23    }
24 }
25
```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/true3.sol:AssetManager=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		2.0	86.6
Storage Removal	False			
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	False			
			Total Instructions	
			1034	

合约 2:

```
1 contract GuessNumber {
2     ...
3     function generateNumber() public onlyOwner {
4         uint256 tmpNumber;
5         assembly {
6             let hash := chainid()
7             mstore(0, hash)
8         }
9         uint256 numbers = uint256(keccak256(abi.encodePacked(blockhash(block.number - 1)))) % 10 + 1;
10        assembly{
11            let chain := mload(0)
12            tmpNumber := mul(chain, numbers)
13        }
14        secretNumber = tmpNumber;
15    }
16    function guess(uint256 number) public payable{
17        require(msg.value >= betPrice && number > 0);
18        if (number == secretNumber){
19            payable(msg.sender).transfer(address(this).balance);
20        }
21    }
22 }
```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/code3.sol:GuessNumber=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	True	test/report/code3.sol:23:13: Warning: Mstore Optimize Defect. mstore(0, hash)	38.1	77.7
Storage Removal	False		Total Instructions 902	
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	False			

Mstore Optimize: 当单个 assembly 代码块包含了未被使用的 mstore 指令时, 在开启优化器的情况下, 该指令可能会被错误地优化掉。

问题 1: 查看检测报告之后, 您是否可以识别合约的安全性?

问题 2: 初次查看该源代码时, 是否能够识别出其中的欺诈行为?

问题 3: 如果没有该检测结果, 您会有多大的概率使用该源代码的应用呢?

合约 3:

```
1  contract gamble {
2      uint public score;
3      uint public betprice;
4      function pointadd() public {
5          score = score + 1;
6          check();
7          score = score - 1;
8      }
9      function check() public payable{
10         if (msg.value < betprice) return;
11         assembly { return(0, 0) }
12     }
13     function getwinner() public{
14         if (score % 100 == 0){
15             payable(msg.sender).transfer(address(this).balance);
16         }
17     }
18 }
```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/code4.sol:Gamble=====
INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec:UNKNOWN INSTRUCTION: opcode

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		0.3	66.3
Storage Removal	True	test/report/code4.sol:15:9: Warning: Storage Removal Defect. score = score - 1		
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	False			
			Total Instructions	
			454	

Storage Removal: 当合约中自定义的函数使用了 **return(0,0)**或 **stop** 指令, 并且这个函数有**多个条件分支**作为可能的退出点时; 如果外部函数调用了这个自定义函数, 并且在调用前后**对同一变量进行了赋值操作**, 那么在启用优化器的情况下, 前一个赋值语句可能会被错误地移除。

问题 1: 查看检测报告之后, 您是否可以识别合约的安全性?

问题 2: 初次查看该源代码时, 是否能够识别出其中的欺诈行为?

问题 3: 如果没有该检测结果, 您会有多大的概率使用该源代码的应用呢?

合约 4:

```

1  contract SimpleBet {
2      address public owner;
3      uint256 public constant WINNING_NUMBER = 7;
4      uint256 public constant BET_AMOUNT = 0.01 ether;
5
6      ...
7      function placeBet() public payable {
8          require(msg.value == BET_AMOUNT, "Bet amount must be 0.01 ether");
9          uint256 randomNumber = _generateRandomNumber();
10         bool win = (randomNumber == WINNING_NUMBER);
11         if (win) {
12             uint256 prizeAmount = BET_AMOUNT * 2;
13             require(address(this).balance >= prizeAmount, "Contract balance is insufficient");
14             payable(msg.sender).transfer(prizeAmount);
15         }
16     }
17     function _generateRandomNumber() private view returns (uint256) {
18         return uint256(keccak256(abi.encodePacked(block.timestamp, msg.sender))) % 10;
19     }
20     ...
21 }
22

```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/true1.sol:SimpleBet=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States		
	Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
	Mstore Optimize	False		42.3	75.5
	Storage Removal	False			
	Keccak Caching	False			
	Immutable Mutation	False			
	Abiencode	False			
				Total Instructions	
				685	

合约 5:

```
1 contract BetGame {
2     ...
3     function bet(uint8 number) public payable {
4         require(msg.value > 0.1 ether, "Must send ether with your bet");
5         bets[msg.sender] = number;
6         values[msg.sender] = msg.value;
7     }
8     function check(uint8 guess1, uint8 guess2) public view returns(uint256 number1, uint
256 number2){
9         uint8 secret = uint8(block.number);
10        assembly{
11            let ptr := mload(0x40)
12            mstore(ptr, secret)
13            mstore(add(ptr, 0x04), guess1)
14            mstore(add(ptr, 0x08), guess2)
15            number1 := keccak256(ptr, 0x08)
16            number2 := keccak256(ptr, 0x0C)
17        }
18    }
19    // two players
20    function startGame() public {
21        (number1, number2) = check(bets[sender1], bets[sender2]);
22        if (number1 > number2) { player1.transfer(values[sender1]+values[sender2]); }
23        else if (number1 < number2) { player2.transfer(values[sender1]+values[sender2]); }
24    }
25 }
```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/code5.sol:BetGame=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		51.3	65.3
Storage Removal	False			
Keccak Caching	True	test/report/code5.sol:37:24: Warning: Keccak Caching Defect. number2 := keccak256(ptr, 0x0C)		
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	False			
			Total Instructions	
			1708	

Keccak Caching: 当内联汇编中出现多个 keccak256 指令，如果哈希操作处理的数据内容相同，并且读取的长度除以 32 的商向上取整相同，编译器在预处理阶段会错误地将这些散列值视为等同。

问题 1: 查看检测报告之后，您是否可以识别合约的安全性？

问题 2: 初次查看该源代码时，是否能够识别出其中的欺诈行为？

问题 3: 如果没有该检测结果，您会有多大的概率使用该源代码的应用呢？

合约 6:

```

1  contract GuessNumber{
2      address public immutable owner;
3      uint256 public immutable betPrice;
4      uint256 private secretNumber;
5      ...
6      function guess(uint256 number) public payable nonReentrant {
7          require(msg.value == betPrice, "Incorrect bet price");
8          bool isCorrect = (number == secretNumber);
9          uint256 prizeAmount = 0;
10         if (isCorrect) {
11             prizeAmount = address(this).balance;
12             payable(msg.sender).transfer(prizeAmount);
13         } else {
14             _updateSecretNumber(number);
15         }
16     }
17     function setSecretNumber(uint256 newSecretNumber) public {
18         require(msg.sender == owner, "Only the owner can set the secret number");
19         secretNumber = newSecretNumber;
20         emit SecretNumberUpdated(secretNumber);
21     }
22     function _updateSecretNumber(uint256 number) internal {
23         secretNumber = uint256(keccak256(abi.encodePacked(block.timestamp,block.difficulty,number))) % 100;
24         emit SecretNumberUpdated(secretNumber);
25     }
26 }

```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/true2.sol:StrangeGuessNumber=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		19.3	91.0
Storage Removal	False			
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	False			
			Total Instructions	
			873	

合约 7:

```

1  contract Lottery {
2      address public immutable owner;
3      address[] public players;
4      uint256 public ticketPrice = 0.01 ether;
5      constructor() {
6          owner = msg.sender;
7      }
8      function buyTicket() public payable {
9          require(msg.value == ticketPrice, "Incorrect ticket price");
10         players.push(msg.sender);
11     }
12     function drawWinner() public {
13         require(msg.sender == owner, "Only the owner can draw a winner");
14         require(players.length > 0, "No players in the lottery");
15
16         uint256 winnerIndex = uint256(keccak256(abi.encode(block.timestamp, b
lock.difficulty))) % players.length;
17         payable(players[winnerIndex]).transfer(address(this).balance);
18         delete players;
19     }
20 }
21

```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/true4.sol:Lottery=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States		
	Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
	Mstore Optimize	False		0.7	78.0
	Storage Removal	False			
	Keccak Caching	False			
	Immutable Mutation	False			
	Abiencode	False			
				Total Instructions	
				948	

合约 8:

```

1  contract GuessNumber {
2      int8 private immutable secretNumber;
3      function generate(int8 numbers) public view returns(int256 hash){
4          bytes32 seed = blockhash(block.number);
5          assembly {
6              mstore(0, numbers)
7              mstore(0x20, seed)
8              hash := keccak256(0, 0x40)
9          }
10         return hash;
11     }
12     function guess(int8 guessNumber) public payable{
13         require(msg.value >= 0.1 ether, "you need to pay 0.1 eth to guess");
14         require(guessNumber > -129 && guessNumber <= 127, "you need to guess a int8 number");
15         int256 hash1 = generate(secretNumber);
16         int256 hash2 = generate(guessNumber);
17         if (hash1 == hash2){
18             uint256 balance = address(this).balance;
19             address payable caller_address = payable(address(msg.sender));
20             caller_address.transfer(balance);
21         }
22     }
23 }

```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/code7.sol:GuessNumber=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
			Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		1.6	81.4
Storage Removal	False			
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	True	test/report/code7.sol:15:13: Warning: Immutable Mutation Defect. mstore(0, numbers) test/report/code7.sol:16:13: Warning: Immutable Mutation Defect. mstore(0x20, seed) test/report/code7.sol:17:13: Warning: Immutable Mutation Defect. hash := keccak256(0, 0x40)		
Abiencode	False			
			Total Instructions	
			510	

Immutable Mutation: 如果在 assembly 内联汇编块中使用不足 32 字节的有符号 immutable 不可变变量, 会造成符号位丢失的情况。

- 问题 1: 查看检测报告之后, 您是否可以识别合约的安全性?
- 问题 2: 初次查看该源代码时, 是否能够识别出其中的欺诈行为?
- 问题 3: 如果没有该检测结果, 您会有多大的概率使用该源代码的应用呢?

合约 9:

```
1 contract Generate {
2     string secretNumber = "123";
3     function generate(uint[2] calldata b) public view returns (bytes32){
4         return keccak256(abi.encodePacked(abi.encode(secretNumber, b)));
5     }
6 }
7 contract Guess {
8     bytes32 public secret;
9     uint[2] seed = [block.number, block.timestamp];
10    function generate_number() public {
11        Generate gen = new Generate();
12        secret = gen.generate(seed);
13    }
14    function guessNumber(string calldata str) public payable {
15        require(msg.value >= 0.1 ether, "you need to pay 0.1 eth to guess");
16        bytes32 guess = keccak256(abi.encodePacked(abi.encode(str, seed)));
17        if (secret == guess){
18            uint256 balance = address(this).balance;
19            address payable caller_address = payable(address(msg.sender));
20            caller_address.transfer(balance);
21        }
22    }
23 }
```

INFO:cfg_builder.sym_exec: ===== Results of test/report/code8.sol:Guess=====

CompileGuard v0.0.1

Scam Detection			Execution States	
Scam	Status	Location	Time	Code Coverage
Mstore Optimize	False		8.8	51.6
Storage Removal	False			
Keccak Caching	False			
Immutable Mutation	False			
Abiencode	True	test/report/code8.sol:12:43: Warning: Abiencode Defect. return keccak256(abi.encodePacked(abi.encode(secretNumber, b))		
			Total Instructions	
			1344	

Abiencode Wrong: 当合约中使用了 abi.encode 函数, 并且其中一个参数是动态大小的变量 (如字符串或字节数组), 同时紧随其后的参数是 uint256 或 bytes32 类型的 calldata 数组时, 就会发生计算错误。

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问题 2: 初次查看该源代码时, 是否能够识别出其中的欺诈行为?

问题 3: 如果没有该检测结果, 您会有多大的概率使用该源代码的应用呢?

第二部分：编译器与智能合约安全

问题 1：您对 Solidity 编译器版本迭代更新的具体内容了解多少？是仅在大版本更新时了解还是小版本的更新都会细致查看？通常是通过什么渠道了解编译器版本更新内容？

问题 2：在阅读智能合约源代码时，您会关注具体的编译器版本号吗？如果关注，是因为什么原因会特别关注呢？如果没有，那么是什么原因忽视了这一点？

问题 3：您在使用智能合约时，是否曾遇到过与编译器版本相关的问题？这些问题对您的使用体验有什么影响？

问题 4：在上述欺诈合约中，利用了 Solidity 中的编译器版本差异。如果这种骗局被恶意使用，您认为它会对普通用户和开发者造成什么影响？

问题 5：您觉得我们设计的工具所提供的检测报告是否清晰易懂？该工具对您阅读合约时有什么帮助？

问题 6：对于防范此类基于编译器版本差异的欺诈行为，您有什么意见或建议？